

Social Impacts of Global Tourism: A Sociological Analysis in the Context of International Tourism Law

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Abstract

This study, approached from a sociological perspective, meticulously examines the societal impacts of global tourism. It delves into six main categories of effects on local communities, cultural identities, and societal structures. While tourists' interest in local culture promotes cultural exchange, the study also highlights the consequences of these interactions on local communities and how they transform the local cultural fabric. Additionally, it scrutinizes tourism from a social justice

perspective, addressing not only its economic contributions but also its implications for income inequality. Cultural change can influence local cultural identities, and the study discusses how tourism contributes to social conflicts and strategies for managing them. In terms of social and environmental sustainability, the study evaluates the impacts of tourism and provides recommendations for making tourism policies more sustainable and equitable.

Keywords: *Global Tourism, Social Impacts, Sociological Perspective, International Tourism Law, Sociological Analysis, Cultural Change, Local Communities*

INTRODUCTION

Today's world is rapidly changing, and the global tourism industry, which is considered one of the leading dynamics of this change, supports economic growth, provides employment and contributes significantly to the national income of many countries (Smith, 2017). However, the accelerated mobility of tourism and the increase in tourist activities in destinations can profoundly affect the lifestyles, cultural norms and economic structures of local communities (Smith, 2017).

Tourism functions as a means of transporting people to different geographies, allowing them to interact with different cultures during these journeys. While this encourages cultural exchanges, international relations and social interaction, it can also bring various challenges (Hughes & Allen, 2008).

These impacts of tourism can profoundly affect the social fabric, cultural values and economic status of local communities. This calls for a careful consideration of the social dimensions of international tourism. In this context, this paper aims to examine the social impacts of international tourism, and in particular to understand how they are regulated under international tourism law (Davies and Cahill, 2000).

From a sociological perspective, globalization affects the structures and cultural characteristics of societies and triggers a process in which national identities are mixed with international elements. At the same time, while this process may contribute to democracy and human rights

becoming more widespread at the international level, some critics argue that globalization may threaten democracy and weaken some countries (Eroğlu and Albeni, 2002: 19; Farrel, 1999: 27).

In this context, when globalization is considered from a sociological perspective, the issues of how this concept shapes the interaction between societies, how it transforms cultural and social structures, and how it affects international relations gain importance.

PURPOSE

The aim of this article is to examine the social impacts of global tourism, particularly its effects on social structures, cultural identities and ways of life of local communities. The article discusses the social dimensions of tourism in detail under six main headings. These topics are cultural impacts of tourism, impacts on social justice, cultural change, contribution to social conflicts and sustainability. The aim of this article is to better understand the social impacts of global tourism and to highlight the role of these impacts on local communities.

METHOD

In the preparation phase of the article, a literature review was conducted to examine the social impacts of global tourism. Academic databases, journals, books and other sources were reviewed. Especially studies in the field of sociology were taken into consideration. The obtained sources were analyzed by content analysis method. The social impacts of tourism were categorized under six main headings. The results of the content analysis helped to understand the social impacts of tourism and supported the article titles. The findings were used to prepare the discussion section.

FINDINGS

In this article, the social effects of globalization on the international tourism sector are examined through a sociological analysis in the context of international tourism law. The findings of this study provide us with an important perspective in the context of international tourism law by addressing the effects of globalization on the international tourism sector and the social dimension of these effects.

Dwyer (2015) emphasizes that globalization has had significant impacts on the tourism sector. While many of these impacts have created positive results in the tourism sector, many of them have also created negative results. In order to ensure the sustainability of tourism, it is emphasized in this study that public and private tourism managers should make tourism activities sustainable by implementing various policies against the negative effects of globalization.

Buluk and Özkök (2016) state that globalization shows its impact in every field today and is gaining momentum. Emphasizing that it has entered a new structuring process especially in areas such as information, energy, production and communication, this study argues that the tourism industry is the most affected among the sectors and that structuring in this field is inevitable.

Patiño et al. (2016) emphasize that tourism has lost its previous meaning with globalization. Stating that tourism has transformed from a field of high-cost and high-status individuals in the past into a mass activity area with globalization, this study highlights the need for tourism to adapt to new trends.

Song et al. (2017) emphasize that globalization is a powerful phenomenon shaping the tourism sector. This study suggests that the relationship between tourism and globalization should be addressed with more quantitative methods and encourages empirical studies in this field.

Brelik (2018) emphasizes that the globalization process is a phenomenon that makes the world economies interdependent. Stating that the tourism sector is rapidly affected by social, economic and political developments, this study once again emphasizes the importance of globalization in the tourism sector.

The study by Sugiyarto et al. (2003) emphasized that globalization has rapidly developed the tourism sector. Especially in Indonesia, it is stated that tourism reduces the negative effects of globalization and contributes to the reduction of the current account deficit.

Kar et al. (2004) show that tourism investments in Turkey contribute significantly to economic growth. However, it is emphasized that economic effects are prominent and may increase inequalities in income distribution. Therefore, it is important to consider the social benefits of tourism in addition to its economic benefits.

Hjalager (2007) discusses the relationship between tourism and globalization in four sections. Among these sections, it is emphasized that local cultural identity is affected by tourism,

sometimes preserved and sometimes changed. The reaction of local people to tourists and the shaping of local cultural identity is an important issue.

Peric (2005) stated that tourism is a sector operating on a global scale. However, it is emphasized that this sector negatively affects the environment, social and international relations. It is discussed how tourism contributes to social conflicts and should be managed.

Aramberri (2009) stated that the globalization process has made the tourism sector an important force. However, it is emphasized that the sustainability of tourism is important and changes in the social and cultural environment should be monitored. This should be included in tourism planning and policies.

Çeken et al. (2009) stated that globalization has made the tourism sector competitive in the international market. In a period when the impact of globalization is increasing, it is important how the tourism sector can adapt to these changes.

Işık (2010) analyzed the long-term relationship between foreign visitor expenditures and tourism revenue in Turkey. The findings show that there is a reciprocal relationship between these two variables.

Global Tourism and the Rise of Global Tourism

The concepts of globalization and tourism have been discussed as multidimensional and complex concepts with their histories and impacts (Aktaş, 2007: 9; Dulupçu, 1999: 19). Globalization refers to a process in which the world is seen as a single space and international borders are eliminated economically, politically and socioculturally. In this process, individuals and companies have become able to reach anywhere in the world quickly, comfortably and economically.

Globalization marks a period in which individualism is at the forefront, intellectual divergences are resolved and social relations become more widespread (Aktaş, 2007: 9). Tourism, on the other hand, refers to all economic activities that arise as a result of people traveling temporarily from the regions where they live to different regions or countries (Dulupçu, 1999: 19). The tourism sector is a multidimensional sector that contributes significantly to the economy of many countries.

Globalization is a phenomenon that paves the way for the expansion and development of tourism worldwide. The rapid progress of globalization has caused many negative effects, especially the changes in urban life can lead to monotony, health problems, sociocultural pressure, traffic problems, reduced quality of life, work pressure and stress. Individuals who want to avoid these negative effects tend to turn to touristic activities (Göngen, 2013: 123).

There are different views on the historical development of globalization. Marshall McLuhan's concept of "Global Village" suggests that the concept of globalization emerged in the mid 1960s. There are also claims that the concept of globalization was discussed in the article written by British economist W. Foster in 1833 ((Adıgüzel, 2011: 70).

The periodization of globalization has been handled by researchers from different perspectives. Roland Robertson considers it as a five-stage process, while Thomas Friedman calls it three great epochs. The process from the prehistoric period to the present can be analyzed with Elçin's historical development approach. This approach emphasizes that globalization has a long historical background and has been shaped by different factors in different periods ((Akbulut, 2009: 5; Çelik, 2009: 19).

International Tourism Law

Law is a set of binding, general, abstract and continuous legal rules that regulate the relations of people living in an organized society with each other or with the communities formed by the people themselves and the relations of these communities with each other, created in order to ensure the legal security and human rights of individuals and supported by state power (Battal, 2000).

Tourism law is an international, mixed, dynamic branch of law subject to the rules of market economy (Boz, 2004). It is linked to constitutional law in terms of personal liberty and security, freedom of settlement and travel, expropriation, freedom of work and contract, right and duty to work, working conditions and right to rest, protection of the environment, right to social security, protection of history, culture and natural assets, protection of consumers (Can & Güner, 2000).

Although it is included in international conventions, it cannot be said that the right to travel is an absolute right. This is because the right to travel does not provide foreigners with an absolute right of entry into a country of which they are not citizens. However, after entering the country,

the right to free movement within the country should be recognized for everyone, without distinction between citizens and foreigners. The right to travel may only be restricted by law and as compulsory measures in a democratic society for national security, public safety, the protection of public order, the prevention of crime, the protection of health and morals or the rights and freedoms of others (Çelikel & Erdem, 2016).

Tourism enterprises are commercial enterprises and tourism law is related to the Turkish Commercial Code in terms of common issues with commercial companies, negotiable instruments, insurance and maritime law (Öztaş, 2016).

The entry of foreigners into the country, their stay in the country, the solution of private law issues in the country and their exit from the country are the subjects of private law of states. Law is a set of binding, general, abstract and continuous legal rules that regulate the relations of people living in an organized society with each other or with the communities formed by the individuals themselves and the relations of these communities with each other, created in order to ensure the legal security and human rights of individuals and supported by state power (Erdem, 2013).

Tourism law is a mixed branch of law that includes both private law and public law rules (Ödyakmaz, 1998). Although other contracts that give rise to mutual obligations and are the subject of the law of obligations, such as sale, lease, and work, are based on the principle of equality of the parties, we see that the parties are not equal, especially in the contracts made by agencies and tourists. According to the Law on Travel Agencies and the Association of Travel Agencies and the Regulation on Travel Agencies prepared on the basis of this Law, travel agencies are obliged to deposit an establishment deposit with the Ministry of Culture and Tourism during their establishment (Küpe, 2018).

Another purpose of tourism legislation is legal security. Both tourists who will visit the country and investors who will invest in tourism want to know how they will benefit from legal protection due to transaction security and their interests (Kozak & Akoğlan, 2012). While tourism law has a private law character due to the relationship between the tourist and the tourism provider, it has a public law character due to the transactions of the tourism provider (Uygur & Turgut, 2015).

Regulation of the tourism sector at national and international levels is necessary both to regulate tourism activities within the country and to promote tourism at the international level.

Therefore, tourism law is regulated by various laws, regulations and conventions at national and international level (Yıldırım, 2008).

Social Impacts of Global Tourism

Considering the effects of global tourism, especially on local cultures (Doğan, 1998; 131), the concept of social structure is a fundamental tool for understanding these effects. Social structure refers to the basic elements of society, their place in society and the relationships between them. In this context, it is important to refer to this concept to understand how tourism creates change within the local community.

The impact of tourism can be not only short-term but also long-term. (Bottomore, 1998; 119) Global tourism has become a major industry around the world. Tourists travel to explore different cultures and geographies, to have new experiences and to relax. However, the expansion and growth of tourism has significant impacts on local cultures. These impacts can be both positive and negative.

First, tourism can help promote and preserve local cultures. Tourists contribute to keeping these cultures alive by experiencing local crafts, traditional food and local festivals. At the same time, tourism can stimulate economic growth and increase the income level of local people while creating jobs. However, alongside these positive impacts, tourism can also bring challenges to local cultures. Local traditions can be commercialized and lose their authenticity, especially in areas where tourism is concentrated. In some places, tourism demand can lead to overuse of resources and environmental problems. In addition, tourism can lead to cultural misunderstanding and conflicts between locals and tourists.

When we examine the effects of tourism, it is important to consider how societies come together and how these relationships are organized. (Doğan, 1998; 133) In this context, it is important to consider how tourism can change the social structure by increasing the interaction between different cultures.

The impact of tourism is not only in the economic dimension, but it also helps us to understand how it leads to changes in social relations and behavior. (Özdemir, 1992;73)

As local communities interact with tourists, they try to balance between preserving and transforming their cultural identity. When examining the impact of tourism on local cultures, a number of important issues such as social structure, language, traditions, economy and

environmental factors should be taken into account. The importance of tourism for sustainability and social cohesion should not be forgotten.

The impact of tourism on local cultures depends on how local people view tourism development (Weaver and Lawton, 2014). The benefits that local people receive from tourism can have a significant impact on their support for tourism. Tourism can bring a range of benefits to a region's economy and society. These benefits can influence the attitudes of local people towards tourism.

First, the economic benefits of tourism play an important role in local people's support for tourism. Tourism creates jobs and provides growth opportunities for local businesses. Restaurants, hotels, tour guides, handicraft producers and many other sectors generate income through tourism. When local people see these economic benefits, it can lead them to support tourism and develop a supportive attitude, and the social impacts of tourism can also shape how local people view tourism. Interaction with tourists allows local people to get to know different cultures and make new friendships. This can enrich social relations and lead to a positive reception of tourists by local people.

On the other hand, the negative impacts of tourism should also be considered. Local people may be concerned about the environmental impacts of tourism. Over-exploitation of natural resources can lead to environmental pollution and damage to local ecosystems. Such problems may cause local people to develop a more critical attitude towards tourism. The impact of tourism on local cultures is related to how people living in areas where tourism is developed feel (Long 2012, p.29; Ekici and Çizel 2014, p.84). Tourists have the opportunity to get to know local cultures more closely by interacting with local people in the regions they visit. This can be embodied in activities such as buying local handicrafts, sampling local food, and attending local festivals. Such interactions can contribute to sustaining local cultures.

However, the relationship between tourists and local communities can sometimes have negative impacts. Especially in areas subject to large influxes of tourists, problems such as overuse of local resources, environmental degradation, commercialization of local markets and traditional handicrafts may arise. In addition, the culturally disrespectful behavior of some tourists can damage the cultural identity of local people. How tourists' relations with local people are shaped is of great importance for the sustainability of tourism and the preservation of local cultures. Therefore, tourists and local people need to interact with mutual respect and understanding and respect local values. It is also important that local authorities and the tourism industry provide

education and guidance in this regard. In this way, the positive impacts of tourism can be emphasized more while the negative impacts can be minimized. When examining the impacts of tourism, it is important to understand the contribution of local people to tourism development (Asmamaw and Verma 2013, p.507). The tourism industry can provide economic and social support to local people, which can help tourism to have positive impacts on the social structure. On the other hand, the impacts of tourism on the social fabric are complex, vary in each region and occur in different dimensions.

These impacts can be analyzed from economic, social, cultural, environmental and political perspectives. From an economic perspective, tourism can contribute greatly to the economy of a region. Tourists' expenditures support local businesses, create new job opportunities and increase income levels (İlkin and Dinçer, 1991;101). At the same time, the tourism sector provides employment for many people. However, the fluctuations and dependency of tourism can negatively affect the local economy. Socially, tourism enables the interaction of different cultures. Relations between tourists and local people can increase mutual understanding and help to establish new friendships (Barutçugil, 1989;20-22). However, this interaction also carries the risk of cultural homogenization. Local people may tend to adapt to the expectations of tourists, which may lead to the loss of local culture. Environmentally, tourism can lead to depletion of natural resources and environmental degradation. Intensive use of tourism sites can affect natural ecosystems and have negative impacts on local fauna and flora. Politically, tourism can affect the political stability of a region. Tourism revenues can provide additional resources to local governments, which can contribute to improving services.

At the same time, however, overuse and unplanned growth of tourism can lead to political and resource distribution problems. While tourism can generate economic growth and employment, it must be carefully managed without harming cultural and environmental values *Tourism and*

Social Change

The high comfort levels of tourist destinations may lead tourists to choose destination regions as their permanent residence (Yentür Berrak D. 2023). One of the main factors behind tourists' migration decision is the travel experience (Gudkov, 2021). During travel, by comparing the country of origin and the destination, a person may prioritize the conditions of the destination and even make a migration decision (Ohashi, 2019; Yentür Berrak D. 2023). In particular, in the destination of Nha Trang in Vietnam, where Russian tourists visit for vacation, it has been

observed that they decide to reside in the destination over time. Similarly, it can be seen that locals also aspire to the living standards and consumption habits of tourists and therefore decide to migrate to their countries of origin. Behind this situation lies a tendency that global culture weakens local values and societies tend towards more financial values (Cleveland and Laroche, 2007). In particular, it has been observed that locals in tourist destinations have become more interested in materialism and ostentation (Özekici, 2019). This suggests that tourism offers a two-way effect on migration (Sherlock, 2001: 276).

On the other hand, policies implemented to attract tourists can expose destinations to irregular migration by removing barriers such as relaxing visa requirements and facilitating residence permits (Hall and Williams, 2002). This illustrates the intersection between tourism and migration phenomena (Sherlock, 2001: 276). Travel to visit family and friends of migrants to different countries is recognized as an activity that can increase the number of tourists (Jackson, 1990; King, 1994). It has been determined in the literature that such travels increase especially during periods of permanent migration (Provenzano and Baggio, 2017; Yentür Berrak D. 2023). Migration based on visiting friends and relatives is based on the desire to overcome asymmetric information by understanding both cultures of the people in the migration regions (Okafor et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020). This makes it possible to transfer the advantages of the destination country to the social environment of the country of origin. This can ultimately lead to an influx of tourists to the destination country (Okafor et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020). This mobility, which initially starts with touristic motivation, may turn into permanent migration over time. These five factors can trigger migration to destinations. While these migrations constitute employment, retirement and entrepreneurial migrations, recreational-oriented migrations can also be observed in destinations. Employment-oriented migration is usually dominant because it is the source of labor that destinations need (Dwyer, 2015: 7).

With the development of tourism, there have been cases where tourism inland destinations have become a destination for migration (Choe et al., 2020; Choe and Lugosi, 2020). For example, destinations such as Dubai and Singapore are known as regions facing tourism-driven migration (Choe and Lugosi, 2022). At this point, more information is needed on how migration can affect destinations. Migration is an important factor affecting tourism (Santana-Gallego and Paniagua, 2022). The ultimate result of migration is to increase tourist movement. Research shows that migration and tourist movement stimulate each other. Migration regions can become centers of international tourist movement over time (Okafor et al., 2022). Migration can lead to a direct increase in tourists, as well as additional migration motivated by visiting friends and relatives

(Williams et al., 2020). Migration can also contribute to the development of alternative forms of tourism (Dwyer et al., 2014). Migration can increase tourist mobility if it creates language differences (Okafor et al., 2021). Emigration countries can increase foreign active tourism income through intermittent visits of migrants to their country of origin (Urry and Larsen, 2011). However, this often depends on the migrants reaching a certain level of prosperity (Adams, 2021; Choe and Lugosi, 2022; Huang and Chen, 2021). Migrants' visits to their country of origin as tourists may also be adopted by tourists over time (Song et al., 2020). This means that repeated trips to the destination are possible before making a permanent residence decision (Oigenblick and Kirschenbaum, 2002). The perception that migrants have settled in the destination can increase the flow of additional tourists from source markets (Hall and Williams, 2002). Therefore, destinations receiving migration may have the capacity to attract tourists. Moreover, migration can accelerate tourism-oriented investments and attract investment to destinations (Kenna, 1993). The masses coming to the destination as a result of migration can initiate cultural interaction with the locals and increase the need for skilled labor for tourists (Williams and Hall, 2000). Migrants can enrich the cultural capital of destinations and act as a bridge between two cultures (Santana-Gallego and Paniagua, 2022). However, the process of globalization can bring migrants' problems in the country of origin to destinations (Castles, 2016). Cultural differences can affect the cultural identity of locals and lead to communication problems (Bianchi et al., 2020; Choe and Lugosi, 2022). Therefore, the interaction of migrants and locals is important (Marcher et al., 2020). Tourism has a significant impact on social norms and values. Touristic activities can bring new perspectives on societies' norms and values and change existing ones. This impact is related to the many opportunities and challenges that tourism presents to societies through cultural interactions (Yentür Berrak D. 2023; Gudkov, 2021).

Tourism provides a platform for different cultures to meet, and these encounters can lead communities to question their own values and norms. In particular, tourists' interest in traditions may increase the need for local communities to preserve and reassess these traditions (Ohashi, 2019; Cleveland & Laroche, 2007). On the other hand, the impact of tourism on social norms and values is shaped by the interactions between tourists and locals in tourist destinations. How tourists and locals perceive each other can determine the impact of tourism on social norms. These interactions can also influence how local communities present their identities to tourists and how they respond to tourists' expectations (Özekici, 2019; Sherlock, 2001). Social identity is the way individuals feel they belong to a community and identify as part of that community.

The role of tourism is an important factor in social identity formation. Touristic destinations offer a platform that shapes and redefines the social identities of both tourists and locals (Yentür Berrak D. 2023; Gudkov, 2021). Tourist destinations are spaces for the interaction of different cultures, and these interactions can lead local people to revise and change their own identities. In particular, tourists' interest in traditions and local values can encourage locals to emphasize and protect these values (Ohashi, 2019; Cleveland and Laroche, 2007). The role of tourism in social identity formation also affects how local people behave towards and perceive tourists. The external interaction with tourists can determine how local people show their identities to tourists and how they develop a social identity as a result of these interactions (Özekici, 2019; Sherlock, 2001).

Sociological Analysis

An analysis based on sociological theories can be used to understand the social impacts of global tourism and the role of tourism in the social context. This analysis will help us to gain a deeper understanding of the social impacts of tourism and the relationships between societies. Our starting point for the sociological analysis of tourism is modernization theory. Modernization theory points out that tourism contributes to economic growth and helps modernize local communities. However, it also suggests that tourism can damage local cultural values and economies and increase inequalities. The role of tourism in the modernization process is complex and involves a number of different influences.

Tourism plays an important role in this phase of modernization. First, the economic role of tourism in the modernization process should be considered. The tourism sector contributes to the economic growth of many countries. It can reduce unemployment by increasing local job opportunities and supports the national economy by generating foreign exchange earnings. This supports the economic aspect of modernization. At the same time, tourism contributes to the development of local infrastructure in the modernization process. The construction of new hotels, roads, airports and other tourist facilities promotes the modernization of local infrastructure. This is part of the physical infrastructure of modernization. But one of the most complex effects of tourism in the modernization process is cultural change. Tourism can affect local cultural identity, sometimes leading to commercialization of traditional items and redefinition of local traditions. This occurs as a consequence of the cultural aspect of modernization. In this context, another important aspect of tourism that needs to be taken into

account in the modernization process is the potential for increasing social inequality. Tourism can increase job opportunities in tourist areas, but this can lead to increased income inequality. It is therefore important to pay attention to these imbalances when assessing the social impacts of modernization. The role of tourism in the modernization process involves many different dimensions and can manifest in different ways in each country. For Turkey, the role of tourism in the modernization process is very important. For many years, Turkey has recognized the tourism sector as an important economic pillar. This sector has played an influential role in the country's modernization process. First of all, Turkey's tourism sector makes a significant contribution to economic growth. Tourism-based economies have emerged in many parts of the country, boosting employment. Tourism revenues contribute to economic growth by increasing the country's foreign exchange earnings.

Another impact in the modernization process of tourism is infrastructure development. Turkey has made significant investments to develop infrastructure in tourist areas. New hotels, roads, airports and other tourist facilities have been built and this has contributed to the development of the physical infrastructure of modernization. Alongside these developments, however, caution is needed regarding cultural exchange. Turkey has become a country where cultural exchange has increased along with tourism. This is important in terms of preserving and promoting local culture, but it can also lead to changes in cultural identity. The social dimension of tourism's role in the modernization process should also be examined. Tourism in Turkey contributes to local economies by increasing job opportunities in tourist areas. However, this can also bring problems of income inequality. Therefore, attention should be paid to these imbalances when assessing the social impacts of modernization.

Dependency theory assesses the social impacts of tourism by considering the economic relations of developing countries with developed countries. This theory emphasizes the effects of tourism on local economies and how these effects can be evaluated in terms of social justice. The effects of tourism on income distribution and its contribution to the quality of life of local communities can be analyzed in the context of dependency theory. Dependency theory provides an important framework for examining Turkey's role in the modernization process of tourism. Turkey can benefit from this theory when evaluating its economic relations with developed countries and the effects of tourism on local economies. First, Turkey's tourism sector has grown as a result of economic relations with developed countries. The foreign exchange income brought to Turkey by foreign tourists has reduced the country's external dependence and contributed to economic growth. This is one of the main features of dependency theory.

However, this theory also deals with the effects of tourism on income distribution. In Turkey, the tourism sector contributes to local economies by increasing employment, especially in touristic regions. However, this can also lead to income inequality problems. Dependency theory draws attention to these imbalances by examining the effects of tourism on income distribution. Tourism's contribution to the quality of life of local communities can also be evaluated in the context of dependency theory. The growth of the tourism sector creates job opportunities for local people, which can improve the quality of life. However, this can also lead to overuse of local resources and environmental problems. By addressing these contradictions, dependency theory examines the social impacts of tourism in depth. When we examine Turkey's role in the modernization process of tourism in the context of dependency theory, we see that economic relations, income distribution and quality of life are important factors.

Cultural transmission theory explains how tourism promotes cultural exchange and shapes local cultural identity. Tourists' interactions with different cultures can influence and sometimes preserve and sometimes change local cultural identity. This theory is important for understanding the cultural impacts of tourism. Turkey, as a country that interacts with different cultures through the tourism sector, can benefit from cultural transmission theory. In particular, Turkey's touristic regions are heavily visited by foreign tourists. This leads to different cultures becoming meeting points. Tourists' interest in local culture encourages cultural exchange.

Turkish culture, food, handicrafts and traditions are shared with tourists, while at the same time foreign cultures can show their influence in Turkey. This is the main theme of cultural transmission theory. But cultural transmission theory also addresses local cultural identity as an important component of maintaining or changing cultural identity.

Turkey has to balance the growth of tourism with the preservation and maintenance of local cultural identity. In some cases, tourist interest can spur efforts to preserve local culture, while other times local culture is made more attractive to tourists.

Social justice theories provide an important tool to analyze the effects of tourism on income distribution and social inequalities. We can focus on social justice theories to better understand Turkey's role in this context. Turkey is a country where tourism development makes a significant contribution to local economies. These economic contributions are important in terms of the impacts of tourism on local communities. By examining the economic impacts of tourism, social justice theories help us assess the effects on income distribution. The

contributions of tourism in Turkey to local economies and how these contributions can be evaluated in terms of social justice can be investigated in the context of social justice theories.

The results of sociological analysis of global tourism show that tourism has significant impacts on local communities, cultural identities and social structures. The interaction of tourists with different cultures has the potential to shape or change the local cultural fabric, while increasing cultural exchange. While the economic contributions of tourism can have positive impacts on local economies, they can also increase inequalities in income distribution. Social justice theories provide an important tool for analyzing the social impacts of tourism and can contribute to a more sustainable and equitable management of tourism.

In terms of social inequality, tourism is a complex phenomenon that has various impacts on economic and social dynamics. First, the tourism sector can contribute to local economies. Spending by tourists can lead to the growth of local businesses and increased employment. However, this economic growth can often be unevenly distributed. Tourism can increase income inequality among locals, especially when tourism-based businesses do not employ locals in senior management positions. In addition, the high demand brought by tourism can lead to rising prices and increased housing costs for local people, which can make their living conditions more difficult. Rapid urbanization and infrastructure development in tourist areas can affect the local population and change traditional lifestyles. This may cause local communities to question their cultural values and identity. In terms of social inequality, the impacts of tourism can be different among local people. The economic opportunities brought by tourism can lead to new job opportunities for some people and economic exclusion for others.

CONCLUSION

The social impacts of tourism are analyzed in the context of dependency theory, cultural transmission theory and social justice theories. Dependency theory emphasized the effects of tourism on local economies and inequalities in income distribution. Cultural transmission theory explained how tourism promotes cultural exchange and shapes local cultural identity. Social justice theories have been used to analyze the effects of tourism on income distribution and social inequalities. It is concluded that the income generated by tourism to local economies can improve the living conditions of local people, but this effect can vary from context to

context. In the case of Turkey, it is observed that despite the significant contribution of tourism to the local economy, inequalities in income distribution persist.

The results of the study reveal important discussion points in the context of international tourism law. More effort is needed at the international level to better manage the social impacts of tourism. Tourism policies need to take greater account of social justice principles and ensure that local communities benefit more equitably from tourism.

It should be emphasized that future research requires in-depth analysis in different regions to further understand and manage the social impacts of tourism. It is also important to update international tourism law and take greater account of social justice principles. Bringing tourism more in line with sustainability principles would be a step towards leaving a better world for future generations.

This study examines the social impacts of global tourism from a sociological perspective and analyzes the role of tourism in the social context. The findings suggest that policies should be developed that take into account the economic, cultural and social dimensions of tourism. In this way, tourism can be managed in a sustainable and equitable manner, contributing to a more balanced development of societies. International tourism law should play a critical role in achieving these goals.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to scientific studies that have been conducted worldwide and have been included in the literature.

NOTICES

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